

Single Fibre Pull-Out Test for the Material Selection of a Hybrid Resin Composite

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Motivation: Hybrid resin composite with a textile woven fabric interlayer

- Lightweight materials and structures gain relevance in the recent years
⇒ Fibre-reinforce plastics
- Clear trend of multi-material solutions
⇒ Joining mechanisms are one crucial key factor
- **Developing of an innovative impregnated textile consisting of an thermoplastic and a thermoset surface**
⇒ Two occurring bonding mechanisms:
 - Bonding: Adhesion forces between the thermoplastic material and the thermoset
 - Form closure: Woven fabric, whose warp and weft yarns alternately change the resin side
- **Objective: Joining due to welding**
- Carbon fibres consist of a sizing, which is usually tailored on only one type of resin
⇒ Trade-off
- **Which fibre has good interface properties on thermoplastics as well as thermosets?**
⇒ **Single fibre pull-out test**

Test device

- Fibre pull-out test can be done by the test devices FIMABOND and FAVIMAT+
 - FIMABOND: Automatic fibre embedding in the resin
 - FAVIMAT+: Implementation of the pull-out test

Quality assurance due to x-ray microscope

Recommendations for fibre embedding

- Knowledge about the tensile strength of the embedded fibre
⇒ Influence on the embedding depth
- Atmospheric nitrogen improves result
- Decrease of the material's viscosity by raising the temperature
- Longer holding times on the melting temperature
- Lower cooling rates
- Lower embedding speeds

Recommendations lead to an improved single fibre embedding and therefore improved pull-out results of a powerful testing device